

Loss of Chance in Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP): An Analytical Medico-Legal Study

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Abstract

The management of Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP) lies in an area of exceptional sensitivity within the domain of medical professional responsibility. ROP is a vaso-proliferative disease affecting the immature retina of preterm infants and is the leading cause of avoidable childhood blindness worldwide. While advances in neonatal intensive care have increased survival among extremely low birth-weight and extremely preterm infants, the cohort at risk for severe ROP has likewise expanded. When not diagnosed and treated promptly, severe ROP inevitably progresses to retinal detachment and total blindness. This study provides a clinical and medico-legal analysis of Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP), focusing on the concept of loss of chance and its implications in cases of delayed diagnosis and treatment.

Keywords: Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP); Retinal Detachment; Blindness; Professional Responsibility.

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INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, approximately 32,300 children each year develop irreversible visual impairment due to ROP, with about 20,000 becoming blind or severely visually impaired [1]. A meta-analysis of 121,618 preterm infants (1985–2021) reported a global prevalence of ROP of 31.9% (95% CI 29.0–34.8%), while severe ROP was estimated at ~7.5% (95% CI 6.5–8.7%) [2]. A Global Burden of Disease 2019 analysis estimated, for individuals <20 years in 2019, standardized prevalence rates per 100,000 of 86.4 for total vision loss due to ROP and 31.6 for complete blindness in childhood or adolescence [3].

In Italy, prevalence varies across cohorts. A multicenter study by Borroni et al. (2013) in infants with birth weight <750 g or gestational age ≤27 weeks (level III NICUs) found that among 421 infants, 62.9% developed ROP; 24.2% had severe posterior forms (P-ROP); and 34% required surgical treatment (laser/anti-VEGF/vitreotomy) [4]. Dani et al. (2021) reported that among 178 infants aged 23+0 to 29+6 weeks, 38% developed some degree of ROP (41 stage 1, 41 stage 2, 14 stage 3) [5].

Human retinal vascularization begins around the 16th week of gestation, normally completing at the nasal periphery by ~36 weeks and at the temporal periphery by ~40 weeks. Premature birth interrupts this process, leaving an avascular retinal area [6]. The pathogenesis of ROP is biphasic: an initial vaso-obliterative phase triggered by hyperoxia (often due to therapeutic oxygen), followed by a vaso-proliferative phase driven by tissue hypoxia and over-expression of VEGF [7].

Diagnosis and prognosis rely on the International Classification (ICROP) [8], updated in 2021 (ICROP3) [9] to incorporate aggressive forms and post-treatment descriptors. Accurate staging is pivotal for probabilistic judgments used in loss-of-chance assessment.

Table 1. Staging of ROP (ICROP3).

ICROP3 Parameter	Definition & Clinical Relevance	Prognostic Implications
Zone I	Circular area centered on the optic disc with a radius twice the disc–fovea distance.	Maximal risk of blindness; very rapid progression.
Zone II	Circular ring from Zone I to the nasal ora serrata.	Intermediate–high risk; requires weekly monitoring.
Zone III	Remaining temporal peripheral retina.	Often associated with spontaneous resolution.
Notch	1–2 clock-hour incursion toward a more posterior zone.	Indicates greater severity than the general zone suggests.
Stage 1	Flat, white demarcation line between vascular and avascular retina.	Low immediate risk; requires follow-up.
ICROP3 Parameter	Definition & Clinical Relevance	Prognostic Implications
Stage 2	Elevated ridge of demarcation (ridge).	Sign of active progression.
Stage 3	Extraretinal fibrovascular proliferation into the vitreous.	Critical stage; often necessitates urgent treatment.
Plus Disease	Posterior pole arteriolar tortuosity and venous dilation.	Primary indicator for treatment (Type 1 ROP).

The term “Aggressive ROP” (A-ROP) [10] replaced AP-ROP, underscoring that severe, fast-progressing disease may present in more peripheral zones and in infants with higher birth weights, especially where oxygen monitoring resources are limited. A diagnosis of A-ROP implies a narrow therapeutic window—often hours to days—for effective intervention.

Because early ROP is clinically silent, prevention of blindness depends on active surveillance. Neonatologists and pediatric ophthalmologists operate within a framework of national and international guidelines – such as the Sistema Nazionale Linee Guida (SNLG) [11] the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) and the American Academy of Ophthalmology (AAO) [12] that establish duties of screening and follow-up.

National guidelines [13] recommend screening all infants with birth weight (BW) ≤ 1500 g or gestational age (GA) ≤ 30 –31 weeks, with extension up to 2000 g when clinical instability, sepsis, or prolonged ventilation are present.

Table 2. Inclusion criteria and screening schedule in preterm infants.

Screening Timeline	Recommended Timing	Medical-Legal Rationale
First exam (GA ≤ 27 wks)	At 31 weeks PMA or at 4 weeks of life (whichever is later).	Peak onset for acute disease.
First exam (GA 28–32 wks)	At 4 weeks postnatal age.	Prevents delayed diagnosis of advanced stages.
Follow-up (Zone I / Plus)	Within 1 week or sooner.	Risk of irreversible progression to detachment.
Follow-up (Zone II / Stage 2)	Every 1–2 weeks.	Assess regression vs progression.
End of screening (Rule 1)	Complete vascularization in Zone III.	No further risk of neovascularization.
End of screening (Rule 2)	PMA 45–50 weeks and no pre-threshold ROP.	Low risk of subsequent active disease.

Non-compliance can arise from omitted examinations or procedural deficiencies such as suboptimal mydriasis (typically achieved with phenylephrine 2.5% and tropicamide) or omission of indirect ophthalmoscopy with scleral indentation, essential to examine the ora serrata.

The transition from laser photocoagulation to intravitreal anti-VEGF agents (bevacizumab, ranibizumab, aflibercept) has reshaped success rates, especially in Zone I disease.

Table 3. Comparative success rates of ROP treatments (no re-treatment).

Treatment	Success Rate (No Re-treatment)	Medical-Scientific Notes
Laser Photocoagulation [13]	89.3% (overall) / 65.9% (Zone I).	Ablates avascular retina; higher myopia risk.
Bevacizumab (IVB) [14]	87% (overall) / 91.2% (Zone I).	Superior results in Zone I.
Ranibizumab (IVR) [13]	74%–80% (0.2 mg dose).	Shorter half-life; requires closer post-injection follow-up.
Aflibercept (IVA) [15]	80.7%–85.5%.	Promising data; fewer long-term studies.

These data suggest that missing a Zone I diagnosis deprives the infant of >91% probability of success with anti-VEGF or ~65% with laser. In Zone II, timely laser achieves ~90% success, making diagnostic omission a near-determinative cause of vision loss.

The aim of this study is to analyze the clinical and medico-legal implications of delayed diagnosis and management of Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP), with particular focus on the quantification of loss of chance through a probabilistic and evidence-based approach.

METHODS

This study is based on a qualitative analytical approach integrating current clinical evidence on Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP) with recent medico-legal developments in Italian jurisprudence. A narrative synthesis of the literature was combined with a conceptual modeling of loss of chance, aiming to provide a structured framework for medico-legal evaluation. Legal sources, including recent Supreme Court decisions, were analyzed to contextualize the application of probabilistic reasoning in damage assessment.

RESULTS

In the context of this narrative review, the following section summarizes and interprets the medico-legal implications of Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP), with particular focus on the concept of loss of chance, based on the integration of current clinical evidence and recent legal developments.

Loss of Chance Damage

Lack of specific documentation in the medical record regarding screening and treatment shifts the burden of proof to the healthcare facility, with a presumption of fault. A further issue is “false reassurance” after treatment: while laser has a definitive effect, anti-VEGF therapies may be followed by late recurrences (often at 45–55 weeks PMA). Failure to monitor after intravitreal injection leads to loss of the “rescue chance”: timely detection of recurrence can enable stabilization; if progression to stages 4–5 occurs, surgical success rates drop drastically.

Recent case law (2024–2025) reframes loss of chance from an evidentiary device to an autonomous legal interest. The Supreme Court (Order No. 18568/2024) [16] set rigorous criteria to avoid compensating in the absence of causal linkage: the injured party must prove the existence of a concrete, appreciable chance at the time of the error.

The causal link between omission (e.g., missed screening) and the lost possibility must be established on the civil standard of “more likely than not” (>50%). Ontologically, loss of chance is a distinct event from the final harm. If untreated ROP had an 80% probability of cure, the physician did not directly cause blindness but destroyed that 80% probability of health.

The system relies on “double nexus” causation. Material causation (A debeatur) assesses whether the conduct was a necessary condition of the loss of chance. In ROP, the missed visit is the antecedent for missing the therapeutic window. Legal causation (Quantum debeatur) selects compensable consequences under Art. 1223 Civil Code [17], evaluating impacts on future life, work capacity, and need for ongoing assistance.

Courts have clarified: if the link to the final damage is proven >50%, compensation is full; if uncertain but a serious chance was lost, compensation is for that chance [18].

Experts must translate epidemiology into a case-specific chance via counterfactual analysis: “What would have happened had guidelines been followed?”

The diagram (Figure 1) illustrates the relationship between initial probability of therapeutic success, delay in diagnosis or treatment, and patient-related risk factors. These variables interact to determine the residual probability of visual outcome and, consequently, the percentage of lost chance attributable to clinical omission.

Figure 1. Conceptual model for estimating loss of chance in Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP).

Note: Chance lost (%) = $P_{initial} - (P_{initial} \times R_{delay} \times R_{risk})$. $P_{initial}$ = initial probability of success (e.g., 91%). F_{delay} = reduction factor due to delay (e.g., from 0.9 to 0.2). F_{risk} = reduction factor due to systemic risks (e.g., 0.8 if sepsis is present). Practical example: If $P_{initial} = 91\%$, if the initial probability is 91%, delay reduces it to 20% (factor 0.22), and systemic risk reduces it by 20% (factor 0.8): $Chance\ lost = 91 - (91 \times 0.22 \times 0.8) \approx 91 - 16 = 75\%$

Premature infants may exhibit neurological or motor deficits independent of ROP [19]. The medico-legal analysis must isolate harm attributable to ophthalmic negligence. If blindness equals 100% visual disability but correctly treated ROP would have caused a 15% residual impairment, the differential damage is 85%, then proportionally reduced if causal uncertainty persists.

Presidential Decree No. 12 of 13 January 2025 [20] introduced uniform parameters nationwide for macro-permanent injuries (>9%), ending disparities among local tables (e.g., Milan vs Rome).

Table 4. Compensation tables 2024–2025 (illustrative comparison).

Degree of Permanent Impairment	Milan Table 2024 [21]	National Unified Table 2025 [22]	Percent difference
90% (Base biological damage)	€819,182.00 (estimate)	€849,836.00 (estimate)	+3.7%
90% (With maximum moral component)	€1,228,773.00 (estimate)	€1,321,494.00 (estimate)	+7.5%

For a newborn who becomes blind due to missed ROP diagnosis, the TUN materially affects compensation. The “moral multiplier” permits adjustment based on the intensity of suffering and disruption of life routines—particularly significant for a child facing lifelong blindness.

The Supreme Court (Ord. No. 18568/2024) [16] bars compensating loss of chance by anchoring it to the entirety of the final biological damage. Correct technique: (1) identify the value of the final damage (e.g., €1,500,000 for severe neonatal disability); (2) apply the percentage corresponding to the lost chance (e.g., 70%); (3) result: €1,050,000 as loss-of-opportunity compensation.

DISCUSSION

Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP) is a significant cause of preventable visual impairment in children worldwide, particularly affecting those born preterm. The condition is characterized by abnormal development of retinal blood

vessels in premature infants, potentially leading to blindness if not diagnosed and treated promptly [23]. This condition has gained recognition not only for its medical implications but also for the associated medical legal concerns, primarily regarding missed diagnoses and the consequent loss of vision.

The present study highlighted that the clinical management of ROP has greatly evolved, with extensive screening protocols established to identify infants at risk [24]. Another systematic review indicated that early intervention and treatment, such as laser photocoagulation, can significantly reduce the risk of severe visual impairment. Accurate diagnosis is essential, as treatment success is closely linked to timely detection; misdiagnosis or missed screening can lead to irreversible consequences [25].

Several studies have quantified the risk factors contributing to the development of ROP, including low birth weight, gestational age, and high oxygen supplementation such as the studies conducted respectively by Hakeem et al., 2012 [26] and Shah et al., 2012 [27]. Infants discharged from Intensive Care Units (ICUs) without comprehensive screening are at a higher risk of developing severe ROP, suggesting a critical need for adherence to screening guidelines as recommended by Koç et al., 2019 [28] Lundgren et al., 2021 [29]. Missed diagnoses not only jeopardize health outcomes for these infants but also raise significant ethical and legal issues.

The increasing prevalence of ROP, alongside improvements in neonatal care, raises the stakes surrounding potential medical malpractice or negligence claims. Infants who sustain vision loss due to undiagnosed ROP or delayed treatment pose challenges to healthcare providers' accountability. Legal actions may arise when parents seek compensation for failures to comply with recommended screening practices or for failing to recognize the signs of ROP [30].

Legal implications can be further accentuated by variable adherence to established screening protocols, which have been shown to differ significantly across healthcare settings [26,24]. Reports indicate that failures in screening practices can lead to more severe incidences of ROP, which, if overlooked, can result in lifelong consequences for the child [31,29].

Clinical evidence underscores the necessity of timely and thorough ROP screening to mitigate future disabilities associated with vision loss in preterm infants [29]. On the other side, the ramifications of negligence or missed diagnoses resonate through the legal landscape, where healthcare providers must navigate complex liability issues and regulatory compliance duties.

The role of medical professionals in adhering to best practices for ROP screening and treatment extends beyond routine care, entwining ethical considerations with legal accountability. As neonatal survival rates improve globally due to advances in medical care, the emphasis on safeguarding these vulnerable populations becomes imperative, both clinically and legally as stated by Blencowe et al., in 2013 [23] and Hellgren et al., in 2016 [27].

CONCLUSION

Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP) represents a paradigmatic condition in which clinical management and medico-legal responsibility are closely intertwined. As neonatal survival continues to improve, the timely identification and treatment of ROP have become essential not only to prevent avoidable blindness but also to mitigate the risk of medico-legal liability associated with missed or delayed diagnosis [32–36].

This narrative review highlights how strict adherence to established screening protocols, accurate clinical documentation, and appropriate follow-up are critical determinants of both clinical outcomes and legal accountability [37–38]. The concept of loss of chance provides a robust analytical framework for evaluating the consequences of clinical omissions, allowing for a proportional and evidence-based quantification of damage in medico-legal settings.

From a clinical perspective, strengthening surveillance systems and ensuring compliance with international and national guidelines remain essential to reduce preventable visual impairment. From a medico-legal standpoint, the integration of probabilistic reasoning into causal assessment represents a key advancement in aligning scientific evidence with judicial evaluation.

Ultimately, improving the management of ROP requires a multidisciplinary approach that integrates neonatology, ophthalmology, and medical law, ensuring that vulnerable preterm infants receive timely and appropriate care while reducing the burden of preventable disability, psychosocial consequences, and stigmatization [39,40].

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